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BALL-ON-PLATE TESTING OF NANOPORE FILLERS FOR TRIBOLOGICALLY EFFECTIVE ANODIZED ALUMINA COATINGS

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Abstract: Aluminum alloys are often anodized (i.e. oxidized electrochemically) to increase surface hardness. However, their tribological properties become very poor mainly due to the abundance of narrow nanopores. Al alloy 1050A was anodized to produce ~ 70 μm thick coatings. Coefficients of Friction (COF) were measured using reciprocal ball-on-plate method against steel leading to COF of 0.7-1. Then anodized specimens were coated with either fluoropolymer PTFE or melted stearic acid, which led to improved wear resistance and reduced COF. In some cases stearic a. was more effective tribologically than PTFE and showed COF of 0.05-0.2 along with better inhibition of rapid wear propagation. Established tendencies could help in developing technologies for the manufacture of tribologically effective anodized Al coatings.

Keywords: aluminum, nanostructure, wear, fluoropolymer.

1. INTRODUCTION

Aluminum alloys are usually soft, but their surface can be oxidized electrochemically to improve hardness. Most often this is accomplished by immersing a manufactured workpiece into H₂SO₄ based electrolyte and anodizing the surface. Positively charged aluminum is attacked by anions (HSO₄⁻, OH⁻, etc.) and oxidized mostly into alumina (Al₂O₃). High purity alumina, like corundum, sapphire, ruby, etc., is very hard. Therefore, the produced surface with an alumina layer on the top, improves the hardness of the workpiece significantly, especially if the layer is thick (sometimes close to 100 μm). Sulfates, oxalates, hydroxides and other compounds also form during the anodization, just at much lower scale. Obtained anodized Al coatings improve paintability, corrosion resistance and most importantly makes the workpiece much harder.

The spectrum of new applications for anodized Al is broadening rapidly, however, in many cases good tribological properties are required. This becomes a problem for the spread of anodized Al, because its resistance to wear is poor and Coefficients of Friction (COF) are very high [1]. The Al₂O₃ layer contains many nanopores, i.e. narrow wells connecting the surface with the Al substrate, through which the electrolyte circulates during the anodization process. Depending on the alloy and anodization parameters, these nanopores vary in diameter, which can comprise from 2 to 100 nm or more. Abundance of such nanopores contributes to high surface roughness and makes it easier for cracks to develop under repetitive loads. Industrially, the problem of poor tribological properties of anodized Al is sometimes solved by applying Teflon™ type fluoropolymer, typically poly tetrafluoro ethylene (PTFE) dry films on the anodized surfaces. However, only limited improvement can be achieved with this technique [2]. It is often debated, whether such polymeric fillers are capable of penetrating into the nanopores of the anodized Al, because PTFE molecules are usually too large in terms of molecular size. A nanopore with ~20 nm in diameter, which is typical in many cases of anodized Al, is already too narrow for a linear molecule of 300 Carbon atoms, while PTFE polymers are often as large as 10 000 C atoms. In addition, PTFE is known for its very low wetting capability, which even further resists the migration of molecules into the nanopores. Nevertheless, the industry still relies on PTFE coatings, such as DuPont™ Dry Film RA Dispersion, in order to impart some lubricity onto the surface of anodized Al.

Researchers have tried to develop various fillers or nanopore sealing technologies, which would improve tribological properties of anodized Al. Most attempts focused on modifying the electrolyte, such as addition of ammonium tetrathiomolybdate [3] and Cerium compounds [2]. However, none of them led to industrially feasible methods on a larger scale. Dry-film approaches have also been investigated [4]. In addition to PTFE, stearic acid has also been one of more popular choices. It is broadly used as a solid lubricant, although it has not established itself as the dominant lubricity

additive for anodized Al. One of the reasons for the limited success of stearic a. is that the mechanisms of its migration into the nanopores have not yet been well understood.

In this study Al alloy was anodized, filled with PTFE or stearic a. and evaluated microscopically. Tribological performance of obtained coatings was compared using a Ball-on-Plate tests.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

A sheet (0.8 mm thickness) of alloy 1050A (Aleris Rolled Products Germany GmbH) was used for the anodization and demonstrated 99.6 % purity (0.34 % Fe, 0.1 % Si, 0.01 % Mn). Stearic a. (Sigma-Aldrich) was reported as 95 % pure. Reagent grade salts and electrolytes were employed for the anodization and laboratory grade solvents were used for cleaning and degreasing. Fluoropolymer-based DryFilm RA/IPA™ dispersion of 25 % solids (DuPont) was reported to contain surfactants (CAS N° 65530-85-0, 24938-91-8 and 9002-84-0). The dispersion was agitated well before each use to achieve full homogeneity and applied as is or diluted with reagent grade isopropanol (Chempur, Czech) on volumetric basis from 25 % to 10 % solids.

As described previously [5], the anodization was performed in H_2SO_4 / oxalic acid electrolyte in compliance with Type III procedures to produce relatively thick, hard coatings. The target thickness was 70 μm . The 1050A sheet was cut into discs-shaped specimens of 1.5 cm OD. Initially the discs were etched in an alkaline solution (30 g/L NaOH + 25g/L Na_3PO_4 + 75 g/L Na_2CO_3) for 30 s at 60°C. After rinsing they were cleaned for 1-2 min in 30% HNO_3 and rinsed again. Then the discs were placed into the continuously mixed electrolyte (175 g/L H_2SO_4 +30 g/L oxalic acid) at 15°C and 200 A/m² anodic current density. Coatings were periodically checked with CM-8825FN device (China) to obtain 60 to 80 μm thicknesses. The anodized discs were immersed into 170 W ultrasonic bath VTUSC3 (Velleman, Belgium) and sonicated at full power for 10 to 20 minutes in deionized water without heat for rinsing. Then the discs were dried at 100 °C for 30 to 60 minutes before tribotesting.

Stearic a. was melted and the anodized specimens immersed for 1 hr at 90 °C. After removal, the coated discs were suspended in the oven for at least 30 min at 90 °C for stearic a. to drip off. Visually only completely transparent layer of solidified stearic a. could be observed on the specimens without any agglomerations of white color. PTFE was applied with or without further dilution to 10% solids. The specimens were immersed for 2-3 minutes then removed and suspended vertically in air for 30 min. Per manufacturer's recommendation the dried specimens were placed into the tube furnace RS 80/500/11 (Nabertherm GmbH, Germany) at 305-310 °C for 5-10 min curing, then cooled to ambient.

Figure 1. Specimen arrangement and trajectory of the linear reciprocating motion in the ball-on-plate configuration of tribology tests. The average friction coefficient for every cycle was calculated from the central segment of the linear path, disregarding 20 % from each end.

For tribological measurements CSM Tribometer (Switzerland) was used. The steel ball (AISI 52100) of 3 mm OD was held stationary. The moving part was the anodized Al specimen (disc), which was mounted on a pre-installed tribometer module and maintained a linear reciprocal motion of 4 mm

amplitude, see Figure 1. At velocity of 2 cm/s each friction cycle produced approx. 100 data points of 'instantaneous' COF, see Figure 2. Under 10 N load in most samples the instantaneous COF values remained sufficiently similar throughout the selected range of the reciprocal motion, i.e. the middle 80% segment. Fig 2 shows that in the vicinity of each end point the values fluctuate more and tend to increase significantly, especially under high friction conditions. This is in agreement with the fact that the movement has to change the direction by 180°, requiring slow-down, full-stop and acceleration to 2 cm/s. Many different samples and test conditions were inspected and it was found that the end-point fluctuations did not extend beyond 10% of the end points. Therefore, the average COF value was obtained by taking an arithmetical average of the modular values for the central 80% segment of the path.

Figure 2. Determination of average COF from the full friction cycle. Anodized Al without any fillers (left chart) shows high friction, while coating with stearic a. (right chart) reduces friction. Two consecutive cycles for each chart are shown for comparison.

Structural analysis was performed on the top surface as well as cross-sections of the anodized specimens, filled with stearic acid. Scanning electron micrographs were obtained using a digital scanning electron microscope model EVO 50 XVP (Oxford Instruments, Analytical Ltd, Leeds, UK). Chromium coatings were applied on all specimens in order to obtain the necessary electrical conductivity on the surface. Magnetron sputtering device Quorum Q150T ES (Judges Scientific Plc, UK) was used for Cr application, leading to the coating thickness of 1.5–2.5 nm. Energy dispersive spectroscopy X-ray maps were obtained at 20 kV on a scanning electron microscope EVO-50 EP (Carl Zeiss SMT) with an Inca X-sight spectrometer (Oxford Instruments). The cross-sections were obtained by two methods: fracturing and slicing. The fracturing was performed using conventional pliers by mechanical breaking of the specimen, whose one side was sturdily fixed in a vise. The slicing technique consisted of two stages. Initially the specimen disc was embedded vertically into a plastic tube, which was later filled with raw epoxy resin and then left for 20–30 h to solidify. Afterwards, the solid cylinder was sliced with the metal cutting blade to produce a cross-section of the specimen, surrounded with epoxy resin. Obtained slices were polished on the machine Tegramin-20 (Struers A/S, Denmark). Progressively finer grades of abrasive cloth were used, followed by the final polishing with the abrasive chromium oxide paste.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Initially the structural properties of the anodized layer were studied. For this purpose, the SEM images were obtained on anodized 1050A alloy. Also, specimens were coated with stearic a. and then fractured to inspect the cross-sectional segments, Figure 3. The nanoporous structure of the anodized Al coatings was clearly evident from SEM images. The top view suggested that the nanopore diameters were mostly 4–6 nm ID, Fig. 3A. One must account for the presence of 1.5–2.5 nm thick Cr coating, when analysing the SEM images. The cross-sectional view showed long vertical tubes, whose diameter appeared larger than that of nanopores. However, the tubes appear hollow under close inspection, which supports the expectation that, if fractured, the coating breaks not through the hollow cavities, but through their intermediate walls. In general, the coating uniformity did not seem perfect. Some nanopores were narrower, their directions were not completely parallel and distances between them varied significantly. Sizeable gaps were clearly visible in the cross-sectional images as dark vertical dashes. They could also be observed in the top surface images as white streaks. Most likely,

these gaps formed during anodization. Deeper portions of the coating developed internal strains, which could lead to cracks and appearance of gaps and segments with different spatial orientation. It is not quite clear how abundant such spatial segments and gaps might be, but considering that the coating is relatively thick (60–80 μm) their presence cannot be disregarded.

Figure 3. Microscopic evaluation of anodized Al coating. A (left): SEM image of the top surface of anodized Al without any fillers. B (right): Cross-sectional SEM of fractured anodized Al specimen, coated with stearic acid. Note the accumulations of solidified stearic acid on the top of the coating.

Importantly, cross-sectional images do not show any evidence that stearic acid could penetrate into the nanopores. To the contrary, from the visual interpretation of Fig. 3 B, it could be suspected that some lumps of stearic acid simply resided on the top of the anodized surface. With the purpose of investigating the depth of stearic acid penetration, elemental mapping was performed on cross-sectional portions of sliced specimens, Fig. 4.

Figure 4. Elemental composition of the cross-sections, obtained by slicing the anodized Al coating with or without stearic acid. The scans were performed by going from the coating surface (low Al contents) through the anodized coating (medium Al) into the substrate (high Al).

Carbon contents showed that stearic acid was not able to penetrate through the whole depth of the nanopores and mostly stayed on the surface. The spike in C contents on the boundary between the anodized layer and the substrate is artifactual, because a small threshold is formed between the two substances during the slicing procedure due to very different hardness. Slightly higher C contents can be detected in less than top 10 μm of the coating, but this statement can be argued, because the increase is very minor. The lack of carbon in the anodized coating agreed well with the SEM observations, which did not show any organic-like inclusions in the vertical tubes or gaps. However, this is somewhat counterintuitive, because the maximum length of stearic acid molecule is less than 2 nm, which is still smaller than the diameter of most nanopores. If diffusion were the only factor, the penetration of stearic acid into the nanopores would be much more evident. The reasons, which prevent migration of stearic acid, might include such factors as rapid reaction of stearic acid with alumina and crystal formation, agglomeration of stearic acid into colloidal arrangements with hydrated aluminum sulfates/oxalates, etc. More studies are needed to explain such resistance towards stearic acid migration.

Nevertheless, at least due to the fact that top 10 μm of the nanopores demonstrated somewhat higher C contents, it was reasonable to expect that filling of coatings with stearic acid would improve tribological performance. Several replicate runs were performed using the described ball-on-plate procedure to

compare the friction tendencies of several specimens. Triplicate runs of empty anodized coatings and coatings, filled with stearic a. are shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5. Reproducibility of the measurements and friction dependence on the presence of stearic a. A (left): anodized Al without fillers. B (right): anodized Al, filled with stearic a.

When testing the empty coatings, essentially from the first friction cycle already it was evident that wear resistance was poor. COF exceeded 0.6 within just 10 friction cycles and continued to increase. Such high friction suggest that destruction processes take place during the test. Despite rapid surface deterioration, the runs of several anodized specimens showed that the repeatability of the experiment (anodizing + tribotesting) was satisfactory. Coatings, filled with stearic a., showed much better tribological performance, demonstrating COF $\sim$ 0.1 until the deterioration started usually beyond 1000 cycles. The moment when the deterioration started did not replicate well. This can be explained by the presence of numerous gaps and spatial segments of different geometrical orientation within the coating. These gaps and segments may lead to removal of larger chunks from the inner coating, which later get into the friction zone. If the chunk is relatively small, it might be ground into fine particles or imbedded back into the coating. However, if the chunk is large, it leads to the removal of more chunks and rapid increase of friction and wear. The distribution of aforementioned gaps and segments is not uniform from coating to coating. Even on the same specimen several wear tracks might lead to substantial deviation in terms of time needed for the deterioration to start.

Figure 6. Friction comparison between coatings with stearic a. and those, coated in 10% and 25% PTFE dispersions.

In addition to stearic a., PTFE coatings were also investigated. Two different dispersion concentrations were used, 10% and 25% solids, leading to thicker coatings of the latter. Their tribological performance was compared as well, see Fig 6. When 10% dispersion was used, a visibly uniform PTFE layer was obtained on the surface without any defects, such as 'fish eyes' or other discontinuities. Nevertheless, the coating was not as effective as that of stearic a. in protecting against wear. The deterioration started in less than 100 friction cycles, which was better than empty coating, but much worse than that of stearic a. However, when 25% dispersion was used, tribologic performance was dramatically better. The latter PTFE coating did not produce any lubricity failure in as many as 28 800 friction cycles, which comprised more than 5 h of tribotesting. After completion of this run the wear track was visible, but the anodized coating was not yet exposed. Evidently, the surface protection mechanism of PTFE is different than that of stearic a. PTFE forms a film on the

surface, which is not removed by the given load and velocity, therefore, the tribological conditions resemble those of steel-on-fluoropolymer without any significant chemical or mechanical involvement of alumina. In case of stearic a., its melting in the friction zone most likely leads to the formation of a tribofilm, in which alumina participates both chemically and mechanically. Such tribofilm is able to protect against wear quite successfully until large chunks of anodized Al coating are removed. In case of PTFE, its film essentially works as a mechanical barrier and performs well only until the anodized coating is exposed. This happens quite rapidly in case of 10 % PTFE sample, but 25 % dispersion produces a much more durable film and is able to protect against wear very successfully.

If usage of PTFE is problematic, the above results show that stearic a. can present a viable solution in resolving the tribologic problems of anodized Al coatings. Further improvement in stearic a. application to the nanostructured coatings can lead to significant advancements in protection against their friction and wear.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Friction properties and wear resistance of anodized Al can be significantly improved by coating them with stearic a. In some cases stearic a. fillers perform better than fluoropolymer-based dry films.

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